

PESA Act and Tribal Welfare in the Globalization Era in India

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Abstract

This paper mainly deals with the effectiveness of PESA act in the tribal areas and also the negative effect of the globalization policy in the implementation of PESA Act in India.

KeyTerms

PESA, Tribal Welfare, Gram Sabha, Natural Resources, Social Activists, Naxals

Introduction

After independence, the Indian Constituent Assembly appointed a Sub-committee under the Chairmanship of Dr. A.V. Thakkar to formulate provisions to safeguard the interests of the tribal population. The Sub-Committee examined the overall situation of the tribals and recommended that it is necessary to provide statutory safeguards to protect the economic life of the tribals and their traditional customs and institutions.

After a long gap, a high level committee under the Chairmanship of Dileep Singh Bhuria, MP, was constituted in June, 1994, to examine the issues relating to the extension of the provisions of Part IX of the Constitution to the Scheduled Areas. The

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committee discussed various issues related to Part IX and examined certain unique characteristics of tribal societies, their own customary laws, traditional practices, community culture, political and administrative systems among others. The Committee submitted its report in January 1995.

Based on the Bhuria Committee Report, the PESA (Panchayat Extension to Scheduled Areas) Act was passed by Parliament and came into effect on 24th December 1996 with keeping in view the welfare and Socio Economic development of the tribals in India. This Act extended the provisions of panchayats to the tribal areas of nine States, namely, Andhra Pradesh, Chattisgarh, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa and Rajasthan that covers Fifth Schedule Areas except other tribal areas of Sixth Schedule who have Tribal Autonomous Council mostly in north eastern states.

The PESA Act is a radical step giving governance powers to the tribal community and recognizes its traditional community rights over local natural resources. This Act has also made it mandatory for the State having scheduled areas to make specific provisions for giving wide-ranging powers to the tribal on matters relating to decision making and development of their community.

Methodology

Data from both primary and secondary sources are collected for the study. The primary data were collected through the consultation of Social Activists those who are engaged in the tribals movement and the secondary data was collected from the Government references.

Local Governance & its functions

The local governance structure of Gram Sabha or the 'village assembly' is not a new concept in the Indian history. A "Chaupal" has always been an integral part of village life where people, generally elderly, would sit together and discuss

current local affairs. All community matters would get decided in these meetings which came to known as village panchayats later. A “Panch” means a prominent local personality and the “Panchayat” refers to the gathering of “Panchas”.

The local government i.e. the three tier structure of Panchayat Raj Institutions in India has been established with the authority of the highest legal entity (the constitution) of the country. The Govt. had thought that with the enforcement of this law, tribals would be able to implement their own ideas that would lead to their progress and the development of their habitat by self governance or Gram Sabha.

It has stated in the PESA Act Under section 4(d) that ‘every Gram Sabha shall be competent to safeguard and preserve the traditions and customs of the local people their cultural identity and community resources. The Gram Sabha is empowered as the competent authority to act the following range of powers:

- the right to be consulted on matters of land acquisition
- the power to control local plans, and resources for such plans including tribal sub-plans
- the power to prevent alienation of land in the Scheduled areas and to take appropriate action to restore any unlawfully alienated land of a Scheduled Tribe
- the power of prior recommendation in granting prospecting license or mining leases for minor minerals as well as for grant of concessions for the exploitation of minor minerals by auction
- the ownership of minor forest produce
- the power to enforce prohibition, or to regulate or restrict the sale and consumption of any intoxicant
- the power to exercise control over money lending to the Scheduled Areas

-the power to exercise control over institutions and functionaries in all social sectors

-the power to issue utilization certificates for government works undertaken in their village

Right to control over natural resources

Procedure should be followed for consultation with Gram Sabha before acquisition of land in Scheduled Areas, for relief and rehabilitation (R &R) and sustainable livelihood plan of persons affected as a result of such acquisition:

Land Acquisition

Section 4(i) provides that the Gram Sabha or the Panchayats should be ‘consulted’ before acquisition of land for any development projects and persons affected by a proposed project should be consulted with Gram Sabha for their rehabilitation and other packages etc. The power envisaged for the Gram Sabha in respect of ‘prevention of land alienation as also restoration of illegally alienated land’. In this context, a clear and categorical provision has been added in the Madhya Pradesh land revenue dept. after the enactment of PESA, which empowers the Gram Sabha of the State to restore the unlawfully alienated lands to the tribal landowners. The unique feature of this law is that if in case the Gram Sabha is unable to restore such lands it has been empowered to sub-divisional officer in this regard who shall restore the possession within 3 months.

Management of Water Bodies

Section 4(j) provides the power for planning and management of the minor water bodies in the Scheduled Areas has been exclusively vested with Gram Sabha or Panchayats. Hence, any construction in the Scheduled Areas should be consulted at the appropriate level before implementation. In the tribal areas ‘Water Body Management’ among many tribes is a dimension of village moral economy or the entire community who are involved in it.

Mining Lease

Sections 4(k) & (1) lay down that the recommendations of the Gram Sabha or the Panchayat at the appropriate level are made mandatory prior to grant of licence for minor minerals in the Scheduled Areas as well as for their auction.

The PESA is one of the progressive legislations for tribal welfare, providing for self-governance and recognizing the traditional rights of tribal communities over natural resources around them. Recognizing the importance of the Fifth Schedule Areas in nine states, the Act provides the Gram Sabha with powers of social audit also.

The second important aspect of PESA is that it spells out a general frame of reference for governance in the Scheduled Areas. It envisages a number of options that may be exercised in each case by the concerned authorities depending on the local situation. It is presumed that the alternative chosen will not violate the general spirit of PESA Act. 'PESA moved from development delivery to empowerment; from implementation to planning; from circumscribed involvement to conscious participation' (Prabhu, 2004:1).

The Power of PESA as Weapon against Naxals

In our country 76 districts are highly infected by the Maoists activities and of these 32 are under PESA districts. The Govt. had thought if the PESA Act is implemented properly that would bring down the overwhelming affects of Maoists on tribals communities and simultaneously, the Govt. assumed some strategies to combat the Maoist movement by implementing this Act. The strategies are (1) If the PESA Act is implemented honestly, it would empower the marginalized tribals so that they can take care of their developmental needs (2) This would deprive the Naxals of their ground support coming to helpless tribals (3) assimilate the 8 percent tribal Adivasis into the mainstream politics

through self governance and (4) To preserve forests and local ecology because they only know their land and its resources the best. But it is fact that lack of willpower, honesty and far sightedness of both the Central and State Governments it has vanished in to the blue. The bureaucratic state machinery has kept intact the self interest with some cosmetic changes about implementation of PESA Act. Hence, the adivasi people never got either the real freedom or sovereignty from the clutches implementation of PESA Act. Under these circumstances, the fifth schedule of the Indian constitution could not be safeguard to the adivasis communities of their own rights.

The Methodology

Data from both primary and secondary sources are collected for the study. The primary data were collected through the consultation of Social Activists those who are engaged in the tribals movement and the secondary data was collected from the Government references.

The Impact of Globalization on Tribals

The Government of India implemented New Economic Policy in 1991 which is deeply associated with globalization. New Economic Policies along with a New Industrial Policy was introduced in 1991. Simultaneously, a New Mining Policy was adopted in 1993 clearing much the obstacles before the big industrialists and corporate plundering of the natural resources. Hence the foreign exploitation of the resources which was continued since the 'independence' had been increased enormously. The mining of the public enterprises have been opened up option of sale to the foreign and private monopolies. In the later phase the mining sector has been opened for 100 percent foreign direct investment (FDI) leading to maximum plunder of natural resources and public sector mining and mines-related industrial companies have been privatized. With these process of opening up, the rules for setting up mine-based plants, sponge iron plants, power plants, dams, infrastructural utilizes,

etc. have been liberalized further with minimum regulations.

India is a mineral-rich country. It has vast geological potential of over 20,000 known mineral deposits, and is in the top ranks in production of some key minerals such as coal, iron ore, chromite, bauxite etc. According to the Geological Survey of India (GSI) the country is yet to tap its complete potential: 'it has huge reserves of important mineral awaiting exploration and exploitation'.

Fortunately or unfortunately in India, almost all of its minerals are in the same regions that hold its greenest forests and most abundant river systems. These lands are also largely inhabited by India's poorest and most marginalized people-the tribals who depend on the very same forests and watersheds for their survival.

Mining as a fuel of war

Bauxite mines, Alumina refineries and Aluminium smelters are being promoted its numerous uses in weapons technology, which make it one of a handful of metals classed as 'strategic' by the U.S. Government, meaning that a top priority of world's most powerful Government is to ensure its constant supply from the third world like India at lowest possible cost.

'Aluminum has become the most important single bulk material of modern warfare. No fighting is possible and no war can be carried to successful conclusion today, without using and destroying vast quantities of aluminum....Aluminum makes fighter and transport planes possible. Aluminum is needed in atomic weapons, both in their manufacture and in their delivery...Aluminum and great quantities of it, spell the difference between victory and defeat..' (Anderson-1951:2)

Development projects and Tribal Displacement

Tribals have paid the highest price of national development because their regions are resource rich; 90 percent of all coal and around 50 percent of the remaining minerals are in their regions. Also the forest, water and other sources abound in their habitat. The indigenous/tribal peoples who constituted 8 percent of the total population of India at 2001 census make up 55 percent of the total displaced persons due to development projects up to 1990. According to the Ministry of Tribal Affairs nearly 85 lakh tribals were displaced until 1990 on account of mega development projects like dams, mining, industries and conservation of forests etc. Lakhs of tribals have been displaced from 1990 onwards due to the so called economic liberalization policies of the Center under pressure from the Western lenders without proper rehabilitation. Yet, no proper study has been conducted in regard to displacement and rehabilitation of tribals.

Prof. Walter Fernandes, noted anthropologist has shown in his research paper: Indian Tribes after Sixty Years-A Study regarding displacement of tribals that at least 60 million or 6 crore people in India have been displaced for the construction of dams, mines, thermal power plants, corridor projects, etc. Among them, 40 percent displaced people are tribals and 20 percent are Dalits, which means the 60 percent displaced people are from the marginalized communities, who sacrificed everything for the sake of 'development' but they themselves are being deprived of the developmental benefits. Recently, India has adopted the policy of promoting the Special Economic Zones (SEZs) for faster Industrial development.

Socio-Economic conditions of Tribal communities

As per their tradition tribals lives in forest and mountainous regions in the close proximity of nature. The economy of the tribals has been

primarily hunting, foraging and shifting cultivation. More than 90 percent of the tribals, to a large extent depend on forest and forests resources for their livelihood. The tribes have been facing many socio-economic and psychological problems since historical times. The large scale land transfers to non-tribals culminated in armed tribal uprisings in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The forest laws since the British time have been curtailing the rights and movement of tribals in forest regions.

Post independence, use of Minor Forest Produces (MFPs) by tribals has been significantly reduces. Exploitation by money lenders and contractors, abysmal poverty, hunger and malnutrition has been the perennial problems for them. Now a days, Land alienation and displacement in the name of 'development' corner them too much. Many tribal groups have virtually reached a state of total extinct or fighting a grim battle for survival.

Development for Whom?

After independence, the Planning Commission in India started the developmental planning in many ways. The Planners and Policy makers of the commission had thought that the best way of achieving development for the common people especially the tribal communities who are marginalized of the country would be brought about by the introduction of Five Year Plan based on both capitalist and socialist model. During the first stages of development, the Commission laid down emphasized on many mega projects like construction of large dams, industries, irrigation projects township etc. and for these, vast areas of land, forests water, mineral resources were acquired from the tribals communities forcibly. There can be no doubt that this model of development has helped the country to emerge as a strong economic and political power in the world but it was at the exchange of cost of the tribals people.

Tribal Resistance and the Red Corridor

While in the last few years an internal conflicts have been intensified in India, the ultra left wing Naxals spreading over large areas from Nepal border to Tamil Nadu. This region largely includes dense forests and tribal areas and consists of 92,000 sq km. popularly known as Red Corridor. The area where the Maoists operate has grown dramatically in last two decades. In the early 1990s only 15 districts in four states were affected by Maoist activities and after that it rose to 55 districts in nine states by the end of 2003 and in 2004 it increased to 156 districts in thirteen states.

At present 76 districts which covers 32 PESA districts areas are highly infected by the Maoists. The resistance struggle of the adivasi people along with the vulnerable sections of the non-advasis had been strongly built up since 1991. Economic liberalization has brought the corporate giants into the region hunting for minerals for their mega size industrial exploits. Industry is wrecking havoc with the living conditions of the tribals under the liberalization regime. Their acts force the helpless tribals to leave the land. Compensation and rehabilitation plans are hardly ever implemented with honesty and dignity. The Adivasis struggle against displacement has spread across the State.

For example, Orissa has the highest percentage of India's total deposits of chromite, bauxite, graphite, manganese ore, dolomite with other rich minerals. The State government has entered into signing of 46 MOUs with different MNCs expecting of an investment of two lakh and fifty thousand crores of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). Simultaneously, this government has invited Hindalco (Birla Group), Alcan (Canada), Vedanta (UK), BHP Billiton (UK), Rio Tinto (UK) with many other big corporate with an investment of nearly 53,000 crores and permitted 7330 lakh tones bauxite extraction of total deposit from the state. All these projects would displace nearly 2.5 lakh families or 10,00,000 people.¹ Against these forceful displacements when resistance is increasing, the

response of the government is highly repressive. In Kalinga Nagar 13 tribals gave life because of their opposition to the Tata Project.

Jharkhand region is a rich of natural resources and many multinational companies have been leased land to build number of natural resources extracting factories. Arcelor Mittal intends to invest US \$ 8.79 billion to set up one of the world's biggest steel plants for which 12000 acres (49 km) of land is required. According to Dayamani Barla, a noted social activist and journalist of that region told us that it would displace forty tribal villages. Adivaasi, Moolvaasi, Astitva Raksha Manch where she associated campaigning, apart from causing massive displacement, the project will destroy the forests in the area. It will also have an impact on the water sources and ecosystems, thereby threatening the environment and the very source of sustenance for indigenous peoples. The tribal people's slogan here 'we will not give an inch of our land'.

At this juncture, Maoists have come forward like other organizations to help the struggles of helpless tribals. But it is not facts that all tribals struggles against uproot are backed by Maoists. But both the Central and State Governments thinks that these tribals are backed by Maoists and only to combat tribals struggles Govts. have deployed para military forces in these regions called 'Salwa Judum' and 'Operation Green hunt'. These spontaneous and non-violent resistances of tribals against displacements have often been misrepresented by the State of their big corporate interests and even by the media at times to label it as a 'Maoist threat'. According to a Public Interest Litigation in the Supreme Court, a chart shows 548 killings, 99 rapes and more than 3000 burnt house by the Salwa Judum in Chattisgarh in last three years.²). About two years ago, the Indian Government launched 'Operation Green Hunt' to root out the Naxals. The security forces of India, comprising hundreds of thousands of paramilitary forces along with scores of police forces are now engaged in a full blown war in the villages of terrains, hills and jungles of central

and eastern India. The Operation is escalated across eight states of the eastern and central-eastern India including Jharkahnd, Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, Bihar and West Bengal.

Thus, bloody conflict between tribal and para military forces has become a daily feature in the tribal areas in India. Recently, passed 'Forest Rights Act-2006 for the rights and protection of forest dwellers have also been violated by the Govt. for the interest of big corporate. The Govt. has been permitting them to procure tribal lands forcefully to set up mining industries, SEZ (special economic zones) etc.

Schemes for the Development of Scheduled Tribes

Efforts made by the Govt. from the beginning of the planned era through various developmental plans, policies, special strategies and programmes. The major schemes/programme for the development of Scheduled tribes are : (a) Special Central Assistance (SCA) for Tribal Sub-Plan (TSP) (b) Grants under Article 275(1) of the Constitution

(a) Special Central Assistance (SCA) for Tribal Sub-Plan

This is a major programme administered by the Ministry and under this grant is provided to the States Governments based on annual allocation made by the Planning Commission. This is treated as an additive to the State Plan, for areas where State Plan provisions are not normally forthcoming to bring about economic development of tribals.

(b) Grants under Article 275(1) of the Constitution

The objectives of the Scheme are promotion of the welfare of Scheduled Tribes and upgradation of the levels of administration in Scheduled Areas. The programs covers all 22 Tribal Sub Plan States and 4 north eastern tribal majority States of the country.

During 2010-11, the Planning commission have provided budgetary support of Rs.1046=00 crore for Special Area Programme-Grant under Article 275(1) of the Constitution of India to the Ministry of Tribal Affairs.

Year	Allocation	Grant-in-aid (released) (Rupees in crore)
2005-06	380=00	380=00
2006-07	400=00	400=00
2007-08	400=00	390=28
2008-09	416=00	339=78
2009-10	1000=00	899=10
2010-11	1046=00	733=10(upto 31-12-'10)

(Source : Ministry of Tribal Affairs-Annual Report-2010-11)

Conclusion

PESA Act of 1996 is the most important piece of legislation for the tribal areas in India. Since the 73rd Constitution Amendment, Panchayats have established themselves as a vital constituent of the democratic polity in India. It has transformed the rural political and social set-up much more than ever before. In the process it also transformed India from the least representative democracy to most represented democracy with more than 30 lakh people's representatives. It also made India the most gender balanced and feminized democratic set-up in the world. (Ministry of Panchayati Raj (2009):

The government called the PESA Act as historic and wished that this Act will help the adivasis to establish

their claims over the land-forest-water (jamin-jangal-jal) but soon the wishes vanished in to the blue. The PESA Act-1996 and Forest Rights Act-2006, there is very weak political will to implement them. Besides, vested interests of rich non-tribals are always to ready to exploits the loop holes on the laws and in collaboration with concerned officials and deprive the poor tribals their basic rights.

In pursuance of the article 46 of the Indian Constitution, the welfare of the Scheduled Tribes (STs) is being looked after by the State government. The Schedule Five of the Indian Constitution empowers the State Governors to modify the State and Central Legislations regarding their applicability to the Scheduled Areas and to frame regulations for good Governance in these areas. But tribal activists informed us that "not even in a single instance, have the Governors responded to their petitions clashes over land, mining or police atrocities except the West Bengal Governor in Nandigram land acquisition case.

Hence, the adivasi people were becoming restless over the forcible and unjust acquisition of land-forest-water and displacement by central/state governments at the time of economic liberalization in India.

The committee 'Development Challenges in Extremist Affected Areas' constituted by Planning Commission of India told in their report only proper implementation of PESA Act can dilute the Maoist activities in the tribal areas.

According to Prof. B.D. Sharma, 'a major cause of confrontation between the tribal people and the state has been the difference in the perceptions about the rights of the tribal people over the forests and their use. The touchstone of the validity of any system and its practices is their harmony with the right to life with dignity of the ordinary people. This right is self-evident and does not need the support of any formal announcement or even adoption in a Constitution. This right is the very essence of human civilization. (Sharma, 2006:6)

Communities in Schedule Five areas today are living through intense hardship, conflict, dispossession, and cultural turmoil. Prof. K.B. Saxena has argued, 'Social oppression, discrimination, bias, poverty and neglect faced by...the tribals have created in large parts of the country's natural, social environment and this history is unknown to most Indians with higher social status and income (Saxena, 2009:7). (Ministry of Panchayati Raj,2009:5)

Recommendations

(i)The PESA Act should be implemented honestly.

(ii) There is a need for awareness generation among the tribal community on the provisions provided in PESA Act. The empowerment of tribal communities, especially those who are cut off from mainstream development, may be possible through PESA.

(iii) A clear and categorical provision should be made in the Panchayati Raj Act or the Revenue Law through a notification under Para 5(1) of the Fifth Schedule or to empower the Gram Sabha to restore the unlawfully alienated land to its lawful owner.

(iv) All pending cases in any Court of Law in which the land of a tribal is alleged to have been illegally transferred or occupied by any person shall stand transferred immediately to the Gram Sabha in whose jurisdiction the land is situated, the disposal shall be made in accordance with the provisions of Section 4(m) (ii) of PESA.

(v) A regular report from the governors with respect to the administration of the Scheduled Areas as provided in the Fifth Schedule and place/table them in the Parliament for discussion.

(vi) Allocation of budget for Fifth Scheduled Areas should be increased by the govt.

(vii) The Audit report of CAG should be submitted every year in the parliament for discussion.

(viii) As recommended by the Prof. B.D Sharma Committee Report on PESA especially with regard to the mining should be implemented immediately.

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